

Market Making Strategies under Different Stochastic Price Dynamics

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Abstract

This project aim is to explore and compare two market-making models under different stochastic price dynamics using Steven`s Shift system limit order book simulator, using real market data. The two main models are the Arithmetic Brownian Motion (drift) model and the Ornstein–Uhlenbeck (mean-reversion) model.

Our main goal is to analyze and evaluate how these two different price dynamic models perform under the same market conditions and under the same market data. During this project the following performance metrics are profitability, inventory risk, drawdowns, and risk-adjusted returns. Both models generate bid and ask quotes based on a certain stochastic formula, both models assume a certain price dynamic, while incorporating certain parameters such as inventory penalty and risk aversion parameters.

The simulation based on the most liquid stocks available AAPL and MSFT, and based on the results, the drift-model generates higher profit and Sharpe ratio, compared to the mean-reversion model, mainly due to holding higher inventory. While mean-reversion models control inventory better, meaning keeping positions closer to neutral. Overall, the results show that selecting a model in market making depends on the required balance between risk and return, including the underlying market conditions.

Keywords

Market Making; High-Frequency Trading; Stochastic Processes; Arithmetic Brownian Motion; Ornstein–Uhlenbeck Process; Mean Reversion; Drift Model; Limit Order Book; Inventory Risk; Algorithmic Trading; SHIFT Trading System; Liquidity Provision; Risk Management

1 Motivation & Literature Review

Market makers in financial markets such as the stock market, option market, crypto exchanges, whether it's centralized or decentralized, their role is to provide liquidity by providing bid-ask quotes. Their goal is to earn the spread, while providing liquidity also to markets which eventually reduces liquidity. The rise of algorithmic and high-frequency trading made price discovery more efficient.

There are several type of high-frequency trading (HFT) or mid-frequency trading (MFT) models exist, while some of tries to exploit latency or uses probability to estimate fill in an order book, or using order book imbalance to churn profits, other methods rely on price dynamics, and their performance depends on how prices evolve. The two main assumptions in terms of price dynamics are mean-reversion and trend-following.

While both methods mean reversion and trend-following can be profitable the key practical problem is which model to choose for real trading environments. While simple logic would suggest trend-following in trending markets and mean-reverting models in mean-reverting environments, previous studies and research suggest that mean-reverting models can be profitable in trending markets, if calibrated properly.

The main motivation and goal of this project is to compare the two models' trend-following vs mean-reverting under the same realistic conditions and to put theory into practical

implementation. For this project the extended Marco Avellaneda, Sasha Stoikov, 2006, model is used which was implemented in *High-frequency market-making with inventory constraints and directional bets* research paper by Pietro Fodra, Mauricio Labadie, 2012. Initially Marco Avellaneda, Sasha Stoikov, introduces a model based on stochastic control theory, where the mid-price of the asset is modeled as a stochastic process, it also introduces a risk aversion parameter and incorporates the order arrival rate in the process. They call it the reservation or indifference price, which defined:

$$r_t = S_t - q_t \gamma \sigma^2 (T - t)$$

Where the Optimal Bid and Ask Quotes defined:

$$p_t^{bid} = r_t - \frac{\delta_t}{2}, p_t^{ask} = r_t + \frac{\delta_t}{2}$$

where δ_t is the optimal spread defined:

$$\delta_t = \gamma \sigma^2 (T - t) + \frac{2}{\gamma} \ln \left(1 + \frac{\gamma}{k} \right)$$

Pietro Fodra and Mauricio Labadie extended the model further, by introducing directional bets makers can benefit from market movements other than just spread capture. The authors introduce a drift-based model for trending markets and a mean-reversion model for range-bound markets.

This research paper will focus on applying and implementing these two models and provide empirical comparison using the SHIFT system. Finally evaluating these models using metrics such as PnL, Inventory risk, Sharpe ratio and Drawdown.

2 Data Collection & Simulation Environment

As mentioned before, the simulation will be performed in the SHIFT system, Steven's own high frequency trading simulator. Which is a simulation trading environment but with actual real trading data, includes the executed trades and sizes at every price. This way we can get a very close back testing result that closely matches real market conditions. It has its own limit order book, with bid-ask prices including marked depth. It's only limitation that data for the Time of Sales is not available. Because the simulation can be run on the same dataset it allows us to test different models under the same conditions.

There are 30 major US listed stocks available in the SHIFT system, however in this experiment, I will only run the simulation on AAPL and MSFT (Apple and Microsoft), as these are two most liquid stocks. High liquidity enables the strategies to run in an environment with continuous order flow, which is very important for evaluating both profitability and risk of our chosen models. Furthermore, running on all the 30 shares would have required a different approach which would get us into portfolio management, which is not the goal of this project. The final simulation was run on April 10, 2026, stock data.

3 Methodology Overview

The aim of the project is to compare two market-making strategies under different stochastic price dynamics. Two models are implemented and tested: a drift-based model using Arithmetic Brownian Motion (ABM) and a mean-reversion model based on the Ornstein-Uhlenbeck (OU) process. The final goal is to analyze how these different models about price behavior impact profitability, risk, and overall trading performance.

The key idea is the generation of optimal bid-ask quotes. Both models produce a reference price based on their model dynamics. Then the reference price is adjusted based on current inventory holdings, this allows the strategy to actively manage risk. The optimal bid-ask spread is calculated around this reference price. This results, that the strategy continuously modifies its quotes in response to both market conditions such as volatility, actual spread and the inventory levels. All orders are submitted as limit orders; unfilled orders are regularly cancelled and replaced to ensure that the strategy remains adaptive to the price changes.

For risk management inventory constraints are implemented, also the model includes risk aversion parameter, which determines the market maker risk in terms of quoting, the smaller the risk aversion parameter the strategy will quote more aggressively. Despite this an inventory penalty parameter included in the models, which controls how quickly the strategy offloads inventory back toward a neutral position. These mechanisms are important to prevent building unwanted positions, which can lead to excess losses.

For performance metrics, profit and loss (PnL), maximum drawdown and Sharpe ratio is used, these can provide a fair comparison of how the two strategies perform.

4 Models Description

So, the two models are called Arithmetic Brownian Motion model with drift and an Ornstein–Uhlenbeck mean-reversion model. As they represent two price dynamic assumptions, based on Pietro Fodra and Mauricio Labadie model, they both calculate the reference price, optimal bid and ask quotes, and both adjust inventory. In short, the drift model assumes that prices can follow a directional trend, while the mean-reversion model assumes that prices tend to move back toward a long-term average.

4.1 Arithmetic Brownian Motion with Drift

The drift model assumption: $dS(t) = b dt + \sigma dW(t)$.

The expected terminal price is: $E_{t,s}[S(T)] = s + b(T - t)$

Therefore, the optimal controls are:

$$\delta_*^\pm = \frac{1}{\gamma} \log \left(1 + \frac{\gamma}{k} \right) + \eta + \frac{1}{2} \gamma \sigma^2 (T - t) \pm (b(T - t) - q[2\eta + \gamma \sigma^2 (T - t)])$$

$$\psi_* = \frac{2}{\gamma} \log \left(1 + \frac{\gamma}{k} \right) + 2\eta + \gamma \sigma^2 (T - t)$$

$$r_* = s + b(T - t) - q(2\eta + \gamma \sigma^2 (T - t))$$

This model supposedly works under such market environments where prices show short-term trending behavior. The reference price is affected by both the current price and the expected directional movement. If the drift is positive, the model will bring the bid price closer to the current mid-price, if the drift is negative, the model will bring the ask price closer to the current mid-price.

In terms of inventory, term q shifts the reservation price depending on the current position. If the market maker is long inventory, the model lowers the reference price to encourage selling and reduce exposure. If the market maker is short inventory, the model raises the reference price to encourage buying. This helps prevent inventory from becoming too large in one direction.

Advantages

- Simple and computationally efficient.
- Useful in trending market conditions.
- Assumed to generate higher profits in trending markets

Disadvantages

- It can generate huge loss if the trend reverses suddenly.
- Performance relies on estimating the drift term accurately.

4.2 Ornstein–Uhlenbeck Mean-Reversion Model

The Ornstein–Uhlenbeck model assumption: $dS(t) = a(\mu - S(t))dt + \sigma dW(t)$.

The expected terminal price is: $E_{t,S}[S(T)] = se^{-a(T-t)} + \mu(1 - e^{-a(T-t)})$

Therefore, the optimal controls are:

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_*^\pm &= \frac{1}{\gamma} \log \left(1 + \frac{\gamma}{k} \right) + \eta + \frac{\gamma\sigma^2}{4a} (1 - e^{-2a(T-t)}) \\ &\pm \left((\mu - s)(1 - e^{-a(T-t)}) - q \left[2\eta + \frac{\gamma\sigma^2}{2a} (1 - e^{-2a(T-t)}) \right] \right) \\ \psi_* &= \frac{2}{\gamma} \log \left(1 + \frac{\gamma}{k} \right) + 2\eta + \frac{\gamma\sigma^2}{2a} (1 - e^{-2a(T-t)}) \\ r_* &= se^{-a(T-t)} + \mu(1 - e^{-a(T-t)}) - q \left(2\eta + \frac{\gamma\sigma^2}{2a} (1 - e^{-2a(T-t)}) \right) \end{aligned}$$

The Ornstein–Uhlenbeck model assumes the price tends to move back toward a long-term average level μ . The parameter determines how quickly the price reverts toward this means. This model is for range-bound market environments. When the current price is below the long-term mean, the model expects the price to rise. When the current price is above the long-term mean, the model expects the price to fall. So, it will shift the bid-ask price accordingly.

Regarding inventory control, the model adjusts the reference price toward the expected future mean-reverting price and adjusts the current inventory position. So, if inventory becomes too positive, the model shifts quotes to encourage selling. If inventory becomes too negative, it shifts quotes to encourage buying. Compared with the drift model, this structure tends to keep inventory more centered around zero.

Advantages

- Assuming more balanced inventory control.
- Performs in stable range-bound trading environment.
- Reduces exposure to large directional inventory positions.

Disadvantages

- Doesn't work in strongly trending markets.

- Requires estimation of the long-term mean μ and mean-reversion speed a .
- More complex to calibrate than the drift model.

4.3 Parameter Explanation

- $S(t)$: asset price at time t
- s : current observed price
- T : terminal time or end of the trading horizon
- t : current time
- $T - t$: remaining time until the end of the trading horizon
- b : drift parameter, representing expected directional price movement
- σ : volatility of the asset price
- $W(t)$: Brownian motion term representing random price shocks
- a : speed of mean reversion in the OU model
- μ : long-term mean price level
- γ : risk aversion parameter
- η : inventory penalty parameter
- q : current inventory position
- k : order arrival intensity parameter
- δ_*^\pm : optimal bid and ask quote adjustments
- ψ_* : optimal bid-ask spread
- r_* : reservation price or reference price

4.4 Order Arrival rate (k)

In theory the order arrival rate k is usually estimated from order arrivals using data from time-and-sales. This requires observing how often market orders arrive at different distances from the mid-price and fitting the trading intensity function $\lambda = A \exp(-k\delta)$. However, in the SHIFT, the time-and-sales data is not available, so estimation of k using actual market order arrivals was not possible. Therefore, I came up with another idea, so I estimated market activity from changes in the best bid and ask sizes in the limit order book. I accumulated negative changes in bid and ask queue sizes, since reductions in displayed size can indicate executions or liquidity removal. The absolute sum of these negative size changes was then used as a proxy for the order arrival intensity parameter k .

5 Strategy Design

The core of the strategy is placing bid and ask limit orders, to capture the bid-ask spread. It fetches the data from the order book in every 1 second, then places limit orders for our two selected stocks, AAPL and MSFT. The strategy runs in a loop during the trading session, which is 6 hours and 30 minutes. At each loop the algorithm fetches the bid-ask price, last traded price, and current inventory position and from that it calculates the mid-price. These parameters are used to estimate model parameters and generate new optimal quotes. Even though the loop runs every second, market data is fetched in every 5 seconds, and the parameters such as drift, volatility, and mean-reversion estimates are updated and 20 samples stored, this way we look back at about 100 seconds of data. Furthermore, inventory limits are implemented with ± 1000 shares to prevent accumulating excessive inventory thus avoiding taking extra risk.

Additionally, the parameter Inventory penalty η , will adjust the model so it will reduce inventory when it's too high. The Risk aversion parameter γ , controls how aggressively the model produces the bid-ask quotes. In this case Order Arrival calculated using negative changes in the order book queue as we assume it means liquidity removal thus trades are taking place.

Finally, all open positions are closed before the market close or the end of the simulation, to prevent holding inventory overnight.

Here is the algorithmic pseudocode to briefly explain the strategy:

```
Algorithm: Market-Making Strategy

Data: Tickers,  $\Delta t$ , inventory limits, runtime T

Initialize SHIFT connection
Subscribe to order book
Initialize price history and model parameters

while trading session is active do
    for each ticker do
        get bid, ask, last price, inventory q

        mid_price = (bid + ask) / 2
        update rolling price history

        estimate:
            drift b
            OU parameters a,  $\mu$ 
            volatility  $\sigma$ 

        calculate:
            adaptive risk aversion  $\gamma$ 
            liquidity parameter k

        if inventory exceeds threshold then
            increase inventory risk
        end

        if model = Drift then
            calculate quotes using ABM model
        else
            calculate quotes using OU model
        end

        submit limit buy/sell orders
        cancel stale orders

    end

    log portfolio and market statistics

    if stop loss reached or session ending then
        flatten all positions
        stop trading
    end
end
```

6 Model Performance

6.1 Overall Performance Comparison

In terms of overall performance, it's clear that the Drift model outperformed the Mean-reversion model on the trading day of 2026-04-10. The drift model has not only achieved higher PnL \$5915, but its Sharpe ratio was higher at 0.051 compared to mean-reversion model's Sharpe at 0.036. These results would make the annualized Share ratios to 41 and 30 respectively, however given the strategies were tested for only one trading day, such high Sharpe ratios might be unrealistic.

In terms of risk, the drift model had much lower minimum PnL -\$274 and max drawdown at \$851, while the mean-reversion model's min PnL is almost 2.5 bigger, and its max drawdown almost twice as big at \$1537 compared to the drift model. This leads us to the conclusion that the drift model handled the risk better on our selected trading day.

Model	Final PnL	Max PnL	Min PnL	Avg Inventory	Max Inventory	Min Inventory	Trades	Sharpe	Annualized Sharpe	Sortino	Max Drawdown	Max Drawdown %	Order Fill Rate %	Size Fill Ratio %
Mean Reversion	5053	5386	-722	54	2100	-1500	9260	0.036728	30	0.039513	1537	0.153575	99.260371	99.260371
Drift	5915	6643	-274	60	1900	-1200	8983	0.051735	41	0.061827	851	0.085051	99.237738	99.237738

Table 1: Final PnL Table

What is more interesting to notice, that the drift model had lower maximum and minimum inventory while its average inventory was higher than the mean reversion models. This suggests overall better inventory management for the drift model.

In terms of total trades and fill ratios there are no significant differences between the two models. Drift model had only 3% less trade than the mean-reversion model.

6.2 Profitability Analysis

By analyzing the Total PnL chart on Figure 1, starting from the market open, it is obvious that the drift models PnL does not fluctuate as much as the mean-reversion model. Also drift model's PnL shoots up to the \$2000 profit territory, while mean-reversion model only catches up the drift model by the 2nd hour. The two models PnL's are close to identical till the middle of the 3rd hour, from that point the drift model handled the quoting and inventory management better, as it led till the market close, overperforming the mean-reversion model.

Figure 1: Total PnL Comparison

Based on Figure 1, the drift model handled the price behavior better in the first and last two hours.

6.3 Risk and Drawdown Analysis

On Figure 2, it is more obvious that the mean reversion model had bigger drawdowns during the trading day. Its drawdown has two big spikes in the 1st and 4th hour. While during the 1st and 2nd hour the drawdowns are smaller compared to the drift model. This indicates that during low volatile periods mean-reversion indeed handles risk better, this provides stable performance.

Figure 2: Drawdown Analysis

6.4 Inventory Behavior Analysis

What we observed at Drawdown Analysis, the Inventory Analysis confirms it. So, the big drawdown in the mean-reversion model is mainly due to the fact that our model accumulated large inventory in the first hour, as can be seen in Figure 3. However, despite the spike in inventory level in the mean-reversion model during the day this model returns the inventory into neutral territory quicker than the drift model, which is expected given its underlying behavior.

Figure 3: Drawdown Analysis

6.5 Realized vs Unrealized PnL

Figure 4 only includes the realized PnL. This shows that most of the initial drawdown comes from unrealized PnL, despite that each model manages quoting and inventory well. Eventually, realized PnL shoots up for both models, and despite some realized loss early of the 4th, both models have stable PnL trajectory.

Figure 4: Realized and Unrealized PnL

In terms of unrealized PnL, on the right side of Figure 4, after the initial fluctuation in the 1st hour, most fluctuations remain close to zero. Showing that positions were frequently closed, and profits

were realized just so. Excluding the 1st hour the low magnitude of unrealized PnL suggests that inventory management were effective.

6.6 Symbol-Level Analysis

In both models, the most profit comes from AAPL, which is mainly due to AAPL's average inventory, through out the day is much higher than MSFT's. While both models had large inventory swings, in both models, the maximum and minimum inventory are almost the same for both stocks.

Model	Ticker	Final Shares	Avg Inventory	Avg Abs Inventory	Max Inventory	Min Inventory	Realized PnL	Unrealized PnL	Avg Market Spread (bps)	Avg Gamma	Avg K	Avg Volatility	Trades	Filled Shares
Mean Reversion	AAPL	900	83	349	2100	-1500	3729	-214	1.372311	0.59	29	0.000251	4821	482100
Mean Reversion	MSFT	-700	25	372	2100	-1100	1492	46	1.09884	0.62	36	0.000264	4439	443900
Drift	AAPL	1100	78	359	1900	-1200	4511	-268	1.300363	0.61	29	0.000261	4658	465800
Drift	MSFT	-100	42	359	1900	-1200	1669	3	1.03982	0.63	36	0.000275	4325	432500

Table 2: Symbol level comparison

In terms of liquidity, average K, order arrival rate that MSFT had higher liquidity than K = 36, while AAPL had only K = 29. Despite this, average gamma values were similar across models.

6.7 Overall Interpretation

The results demonstrate the trade-off between profitability and inventory management. Under the dataset on 2026-04-10, the drift model outperformed the mean-reversion strategy in both profitability and risk-adjusted returns, while the mean-reversion model had more stable inventory control after the 1st hour and reduced directional exposure.

Summing up the main conclusions:

- Drift model:
 - Highest PnL
 - Best risk-adjusted performance in terms of Sharpe ratio
 - Lower drawdowns
- Mean-Reversion model:
 - Quicker inventory reduction
 - Balanced quoting behavior

Mean Reversion		Drift	
Metric	Value	Metric	Value
Final PnL	5053	Final PnL	5915
Max PnL	5386	Max PnL	6643
Min PnL	-722	Min PnL	-274
Avg Inventory	54	Avg Inventory	60
Max Inventory	2100	Max Inventory	1900
Min Inventory	-1500	Min Inventory	-1200
Trades	9260	Trades	8983
Sharpe	0.036728	Sharpe	0.051735
Annualized Sharpe	30	Annualized Sharpe	41
Max Drawdown	1537	Max Drawdown	851
Order Fill Rate %	99.26037	Order Fill Rate %	99.23774

Table 3: Final Pnl Comparison

7 Conclusions and Limitations

Finally, the overall conclusion is that we cannot say that one model is superior to the other, there is no universally better model as performance depends on market conditions and risk preference. As we've seen so far taking directional bets can improve PnL, however inventory management is mostly responsible for risk and profits.

However, it is worth mentioning the limitations of this study, the results are based on a only two stocks traded during a single trading day. Moreover, the simulation does not account for transaction costs, commissions, or latency. Also, the SHIFT environment does not provide time-and-sales data, making it impossible to directly calibrate the order arrival rate, according to the original formula use in Marco Avellaneda, Sasha Stoikov, 2006, High-frequency trading in a limit order book.

For future studies, incorporating transaction costs and latency effects could provide more realistic results. Additionally implementing market regime detection methods using Markov chains and exploring reinforcement learning approaches to improve profitability while reducing inventory risk, could lead to better risk adjusted returns.

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